

DEPLOYMENT OF THE WEB-GIS APPLICATION TO STORJ (AWS S3 COMPATIBLE) CLOUD STORAGE

Speaking about single page web-GIS applications there is always a question about the “flexibility of such architecture”. In other words: can we use the same logic and component structure of the client-side web-GIS application, but with other spatial data sources? Or can we replace a folder of geoJSON files with REST API endpoints or vector tile storage?

The short answer is: “Yes, for sure”. To prove that, another version of the “Web Atlas of Demography” was created, where the same client-side web-GIS application received data from another source. To make the experiment more complex, a major decision was made to replace all geoJSON files with vector tile layers. But a question appeared: where to store all datasets with a huge number of .pbf files?

Storj – S3-compatible object storage built on the distributed cloud. And it was a good chance to implement decentralized cloud storage into “serverless” web-GIS application architecture.

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Web Atlas of Demography is a web-based geographic information system, which is developed with only open-source technologies and free public data. The main idea behind this application is a “serverless architecture”, meaning that all configuration and programming logic is stored on client-side.

According to this approach, web-GIS application and all spatial data (.pbf vector tiles) are deployed to Storj – object storage built on the distributed cloud (AWS S3-compatible). Creating two separate buckets (for web hosting and for spatial data) inside of the Storj project allows to work independently with data sources and the web-GIS application.

The main stages of the Storj decentralized cloud storage implementation:

1. Registering a free account at Storj
2. Creating 2 buckets within the Project:
 - Bucket#1 (web hosting) – where client-side web-GIS application will be deployed
 - Bucket#2 (vector tiles storage) – where folders with .pbf files will be stored
3. Conversion of geoJSON files into vector tiles (.pbf) with Tippecanoe CLI
4. Uploading the final build of the client-side web-GIS application to Bucket#1 with Uplink CLI
5. Uploading folders with more than 6000 .pbf files to Bucket#2 with Uplink CLI
6. Registering a new subdomain in DNS-provider (CloudFlare) and creating additional records CNAME, TXT, TXT, which point out to Bucket#1, where web-GIS application was deployed.

Conclusion

- Storj offers a “Free plan” with 25Gb of cloud storage and 25Gb of egress per month, which is totally enough to become familiar with the cloud infrastructure and even run a scientific project like the web-atlas prototype
- Uplink Command Line Interface – is a reliable and easy to use tool for cloud storage management and file transfer (even recursively)
- Storj – is fully compatible with AWS S3 storage, so “AWS SDK for JavaScript” could be used by web-developers directly in the browser or at server-side (Node.js)
- web-GIS app became faster and more lightweight for web browser because “client” is only responsible for rendering the tiles;
- everybody can try the new version of the “serverless” web-GIS application and estimate the increase in performance: <https://atlas-storj.geohub.org.ua/>